

Application of zinc salts effectively minimized the problem at some locations where it was severe. We suspect that zinc deficiency threatens higher yields in intensive rice cropping areas with alkaline and saline soils.

The cheapest way to handle the problem where available soil zinc is above the critical level is to dry the soil between two rice crops. In soils with low zinc, zinc sulfate or zinc oxide should be applied along with the normally applied fertilizers. Such requirement would mean additional input costs for many Bangladesh farmers. ■

Coastal saline soils in the Philippines as potential rice lands

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To ascertain the potential of Philippine coastal saline soils as rice lands, the performance of a total of 26 salt-tolerant rices was studied in 24 replicated experiments at 14 sites in farmers' fields from 1977 to 1979. The soils at the sites were characterized chemically and hydrologically, and the salt dynamics was monitored. The plants were scored visually for salt injury.

The soils ranged from 4.4 to 7.8 in pH, from 1.3 to 15.4% in organic matter content, and from moderate to high in nutrient status. Of the high-pH soils, seven were zinc deficient and two were boron toxic. The two strongly acid soils were iron toxic. Intrusion of seawater, saline creek water, or saline groundwater affected all 14 sites, especially in the dry season; deep flooding in the wet season occurred at 4 sites. The salt concentration increased during the dry season and decreased in the wet. EC values ranged from 1 to 15 mmho/cm during the year.

The performance of the rices varied with salt concentration, water availability in the dry season, and flood damage in the wet season. On slightly saline soils not subject to drought or deep flooding, the salt-tolerant pest-resistant semidwarfs

IR42, IR2071-105-4, IR2307-247-2, IR4619-48-3, IR4630-22-2, IR9884-3-3, and IR9884-54-3 yielded more than 4 t/ha.

There is promise that yields on current

saline rice fields can be increased and that coastal soils where salinity and flooding are not severe can be made into productive rice lands without costly inputs. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Design of a deepwater tank for ufra research

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In previous varietal screening in Bangladesh against ufra disease of deepwater rice (caused by stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* Filipjev), leaf sheaths were inoculated with nematodes to achieve adequate infestation. This procedure may not be appropriate because it does not help detect sources of resistance on the basis of difference in the surface properties of the rice plant, e.g. how smooth or how tightly wrapped the leaf sheaths are. These properties could be particularly important under natural conditions

because they enable the nematodes to move from the water, through which they spread and reach the young tissues on which they feed. Therefore a special deepwater tank (see figure) was constructed at BRRI to simulate natural infestation under controlled conditions on a large scale.

The main experimental tank (20- X 20-m area, 2 m deep), whose walls are made of earth, is supplied with water from a tubewell. The water level can be maintained at 0.5 m, in spite of irregular rainfall, by inserting a constant level device in the drain conduit. It is important that water leaving the tank complex contain no live nematodes that might infest farmers' fields or nearby experimental sites. The water is led through a series of sedimentation chambers arranged in a row along one wall of the tank. The concrete-lined

A deepwater tank for ufra research, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute. (Note the sedimentation chambers along the far wall of the tank, and the use of polythene cages and miniature deepwater tanks to partition the main tank.)